

Perceived Stress Among Medical Undergraduates and it's Correlation with Psychosomatic Stress: A Cross Sectional StudyGarima Singh¹, Namita², Himanshu Nirvan³, Niraj Srivastava⁴¹Associate Professor, Department of Physiology, Noida International Institute of Medical Sciences (NIU), Gautam Buddha Nagar, U.P. *Corresponding Author²Assistant Professor, Department of Physiology, Rajarshi Dashrath Autonomous State Medical College, Ayodhya, U.P.³ Assistant Professor, Department of Psychiatry, Noida International Institute of Medical Sciences (NIU), Gautam Buddha Nagar, U.P.⁴ HOD, Department of Physiology, Rama Medical College, Hospital and Research Centre, Hapur, U.P.

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Abstract:

Perceived stress among students makes them vulnerable to psychological problems which leads to poor academic performance and affects their physical and mental well-being. The aim of present study is early detection of perceived stress among medical undergraduates and its association with psychosomatic symptoms. This cross-sectional study was conducted on MBBS undergraduates studying in second semester. The study group included a total of 51 medical graduates aged between 18-22 years with similar sociodemographic profile. Stress level of the students was assessed using Perceived Stress Scale-10 (PSS-10) and psychosomatic symptoms using Psychosomatic symptoms questionnaire (SSS).

Average total PSS score (mean \pm SD) among the participants was 20.9 ± 6.66 and the mean PSQ score among the participants was 44.0 ± 16.8 . Statistically significant difference was found in the PSS score between males and females ($p = 0.0011$) with females having higher mean score. Significant negative correlation between the two scores was present among the participants ($p < 0.0001$). Significant difference was present in the PSQ score among the low, moderate and high perceived stress groups ($p = 0.0006$).

We conclude that medical undergraduates perceive high amount of stress and the higher level of stress is associated with more frequent psychosomatic symptoms.

Keywords: Medical undergraduates, Perceived stress, Psychosomatic symptoms

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Introduction

Stress can be defined as any uncomfortable emotional experience accompanied by predictable biochemical, physiological and behavioral changes. Stress is a normal reaction of body to everyday pressures, but it can become unhealthy when it upsets your day-to-day functioning, health and your work efficiency. By causing mind-body changes, stress leads directly to psychological and physiological diseases and disorder and reduces quality of life [1]. There are various factors that contribute to stress in young adults like high academic demands, increased work pressure, inadequate support from family, peers and seniors, having no control over the life situations, being a victim of bullying or having poor relationships [2,3]. Higher level of stress causes fluctuation in the level of neurohormonal factors like cortisol which can have adverse physical and psychological effects. It can also have effect on the brain structure and function and thus can impairing the cognitive functions [4]. Stress may have a

negative impact on the student's cognitive abilities like thinking, learning, recall, memory and problem solving. Excessive stress may result in mental and physical problems and may diminish a student's sense of worth and might affect his/her academic achievement[5].

Perceived stress is the ability of an individual to feel the general stressfulness of life and their ability to handle such stress [6]. Literature have mentioned that perceived stress is associated with the functional and structural changes in the prefrontal cortex and is a predictor for depressive symptoms [7]. Research findings suggest that, persistently high stress may lead to anxiety and depression. The level of perceived stress can differ according to the courses which the students are learning and also there are gender related differences [6].

A direct effect of perceived stress on psychosomatic symptoms have been found in the past. Several

studies have reported an association between stressful working conditions and psychosomatic symptoms (PSS). Studies indicate that stressful working conditions can interfere with physiological and psychological well-being [8]. The most frequent PSS are sleeping problems, palpitation, stress related diarrhoea, chronic fatigue and back pain [9].

In this study we have tried to evaluate the level of stress perceived by the medical undergraduate students in their initial year of academic life and its relation with psychosomatic symptoms. Numerous researchers have evaluated stress in medical undergraduates using various instruments at various levels [10-13]. The most used instrument is Perceived Stress Scale-10. The Perceived Stress Scale (PSS) is an easy-to-use questionnaire with established acceptable psychometric properties. It is one of the most popular tools for measuring psychological stress. It is a self-reported questionnaire that measures the degree to which an individual assesses situations in his life as stressful [14]. Somatic Symptom Scale is a reliable and valid self-reported measurement of somatic symptom. It has excellent item characteristics and the questionnaire includes a wide range of symptoms including gastrointestinal, cardiac, respiratory, physical fatigue, musculoskeletal, cognitive, and other symptoms [15].

With new life challenges, demands and transitioning into a newer and tougher academic curriculum, medical students are speculated to experience more stress. Our study has tried to address this issue which is adversely affecting the physiological and psychological well-being of the students.

Materials and Method:

Cross sectional study was conducted among medical graduates aged between 18-22 years. Students from second semester of medical college in Greater Noida were invited to participate in the study, their health, academic performance, and level of perceived stress was evaluated

Inclusion criteria

1. Healthy adults of the age above 18 yrs.
2. No developmental disabilities (e.g., autism, developmental delay), functionally impaired.
3. Students giving informed written consent to participate in the study.

Exclusion criteria

1. Diagnosed case of major medical illness like Asthma, hypertension, DM, cancer etc.

2. Pre-existing case of major neurologic or psychiatric disorder.
3. H/O substance or drug abuse.

Procedure:

Healthy adults of the age above 18 yrs. satisfying the inclusion and exclusion criteria and ready to participate in the study were included in the study. The participant's demographic information and clinical history was taken. 74 students gave written informed consent for participation in the study and 51 students completed the Perceived Stress Scale-10 (PSS-10) and Somatic Symptom Scale (SSS) using an online survey system [15,16].

There were 10 items in the Perceived Stress Scale. PSS scores was obtained by reversing responses (e.g., 0 = 4, 1 = 3, 2 = 2, 3 = 1 & 4 = 0) to the four positively stated items (items 4, 5, 7, & 8) and then summing across all scale items. Individual scores on the PSS can range from 0 to 40 with higher scores indicating higher perceived stress. Scores ranging from 0-13 is considered low stress. Scores ranging from 14-26 is considered moderate stress and scores ranging from 27-40 is considered high perceived stress [16].

Psychosomatic symptoms questionnaire (PSQ) questionnaire includes symptoms like headache, anxiety, insomnia, anger, depression, diarrhoea, gastritis, constipation, irritability, fatigue, restlessness, itching, tingling and the scoring was done on the basis of frequency of the symptoms. The responses were scored as follows: 0-Almost all day, Every day 1-Once or twice daily, 2- Every night or day, 3- two to three times per week, 4- Once a week, 5-once a month, 6-Never. [15]

Results

Total number of participants in this study was 51. 43.14% of the participants were females and 56.86% were males. All the students were in the second semester and studying in the same institute with similar sociodemographic profile. The mean age of the participants was 19.7 ± 1.02 years.

Table 1 shows the mean total PSS score and individual item score. Total PSS score (mean \pm SD) among the participants was 20.9 ± 6.66 . The highest average score was for the question 8, the reverse scoring of which indicate that they often didn't have this feeling that they are on top of things. Question 3 also had high mean score value which shows that participants often have felt nervous and stressed.

Table 1: Individual item score and total PSS score (mean \pm SD) among the participants.

PSS items	QUESTION	MEAN \pm SD
1	In the last month, how often have you been upset because of something that happened unexpectedly?	2.24 \pm 1.18
2	In the last month, how often have you felt that you were unable to control the important things in your life?	2.24 \pm 1.26
3	In the last month, how often have you felt nervous and stressed?	2.45 \pm 1.10
4	In the last month, how often have you felt confident about your ability to handle your personal problems?	1.57 \pm 0.985
5	In the last month, how often have you felt that things were going your way?	2.12 \pm 0.973
6	In the last month, how often have you found that you could not cope with all the things that you had to do?	1.78 \pm 1.21
7	In the last month, how often have you been able to control irritations in your life?	1.88 \pm 1.03
8	In the last month, how often have you felt that you were on top of things?	2.59 \pm 0.853
9	In the last month, how often have you been angered because of things that happened that were outside of your control?	2.12 \pm 1.28
10	In the last month, how often have you felt difficulties were piling up so high that you could not overcome them?	1.94 \pm 1.10
	TOTAL PSS SCORE	20.9 \pm 6.66

Statistically significant difference was also found in the PSS score between males and females ($p = 0.0011$) with females having higher mean score indicating higher perceived stress level (Figure 1)

Based on the total PSS score it was found that 8 participants had low stress, 36 had moderate stress and 7 had high perceived stress. Thus, total of 70.59% of the participants were experiencing moderate stress. The mean PSS score for the low, moderate and high stress groups were 10.63 ± 2.066 , 21.08 ± 3.581 and 31.86 ± 2.968 respectively. The total mean PSQ score was 44.0 ± 16.8 . No statistically significant difference was found in the

PSQ score between male and female participants ($p = 0.158$). Figure 2 – 6 shows the correlation between PSS score and PSQ score among the study participants. A negative correlation between the two scores was present among total participants, among males and females, and among mild, moderate perceived stress groups. No statistically significant relation was found in the severe perceived stress group.

Figure 2: Correlation between PSS score and PSQ score among the participants (n=51).

PSS = Perceived Stress Scale, PSQ = Psychosomatic Symptom Questionnaire
 Test applied Spearman r. * $p < 0.05$ taken as significant

Figure 3: Correlation between PSS score and PSQ score among male participants (n= 29).

PSS = Perceived Stress Scale, PSQ = Psychosomatic Symptom Questionnaire
 Test applied Spearman r. * $p < 0.05$ taken as significant

Figure 4: Correlation between PSS score and PSQ score among the female participants (n=22).

PSS = Perceived Stress Scale, PSQ = Psychosomatic Symptom Questionnaire
 Test applied Spearman r. * $p < 0.05$ taken as significant

Figure 5: Correlation between PSS score and PSQ score among the mild perceived stress group (n=8).

PSS = Perceived Stress Scale, PSQ = Psychosomatic Symptom Questionnaire
 Test applied Spearman r. * $p < 0.05$ taken as significant

Figure 6: Correlation between PSS score and PSQ score among the moderate perceived stress group (n=36).

PSS = Perceived Stress Scale, PSQ = Psychosomatic Symptom Questionnaire
 Test applied Spearman r. *p<0.05 taken as significant

Table 2 shows ANOVA and post hoc analysis of the PSQ score among low, moderate and high perceived stress groups. ANOVA and multiple pairwise comparisons were done for the three groups. Significant difference was present among the three groups with maximum statistically significant difference between low and high perceived stress group.

Table 2: Multiple pairwise comparison among low, moderate and high perceived stress groups for the PSQ score .

COMPARISON	Z	P value of multiple comparison	ANOVA p value
Low perceived stress vs Moderate perceived stress	2.682	0.0220	0.0006
Low perceived stress vs High perceived stress	3.853	0.0003	
Moderate perceived stress vs High perceived stress	2.290	0.0660	

PSQ = Psychosomatic Symptom Questionnaire. Test applied Kruskal-Wallis test and Dunn’s multiple comparison test. *p<0.05 taken as significant.

Discussion

The present study was conducted to assess the stress level perceived by the MBBS second semester students, the presence of somatosensory symptoms and the relation between the two. All the students were within the age range of 18 to 22 years with mean age 19.7±1.02 years. Among the participants 43.14% of the participants were females and 56.86% were males. Reis RS et al. (2010) in their study reported that PSS-10 score demonstrate adequate internal consistency and reliability with Cronbach’s alpha coefficients 0.87 for the total Score [17]. The questionnaire used for somatosensory symptoms also have excellent item characteristics and good reliability (Cronbach α = 0.81) [15].

Academic stress is considered as one of the main contributory factor among the young adults. The average PSS score indicates that our participants were mainly experiencing moderate amount of stress. Also, the individual item scores were mainly in the moderate to high perceived stress range (Table 1). On the basis of individual item score it was very clear that they were often experiencing nervousness and stress, losing control over important things in life, upset about unexpected events and didn’t have command or control over things (Table 1). Our finding is similar to other studies done in the past

[18,19,20]. It was also evident that the stress perceived by females was more than the males. Studies report that females are more vulnerable to stressful situations and they feel higher levels of stress than their male counterparts [21,22]. The reason for the higher level of stress experienced by female students may be due to neuroendocrine factors, neurobiological factors and genetic vulnerability. Furthermore, social factors like the concept of masculinity and femininity can affect the attitude and behaviour towards the life experiences [23,24].

Stress is very common in medical under graduate students and health care professionals. In our study 70.59% of the students were experiencing moderate amount of stress and 13.72% were experiencing high stress level. Our study result is in concordance with the study findings done in the past [25,26].

All the students in our study were in the second semester of the MBBS curriculum. Undergraduate college students in the first year of college life often experience several life-changing events and challenges. High academic demands, parent’s expectations, living away from home for the first time, peer pressure and developing new relationships are some of the challenges [27].

Further, we evaluated participant's psychosomatic symptoms through Psychosomatic Symptom Questionnaire. The psychosomatic symptoms are characterized by physical or bodily complaints which cannot be fully explained by organic reasons. The questionnaire comprised a scale which not only included a wide range of symptoms but also the severity on the basis of frequency of their occurrence. We studied relation between PSS and PSQ score. Significant negative correlation was found between the two scores, emphasizing the presence of various psychosomatic symptoms among students perceiving high level of stress (Fig. 2-6). Multiple pairwise comparison showed a clear difference in the reported psychosomatic symptoms among the low, moderate and high perceived stress groups. No statistically significant difference was present between moderate and high perceived stress group and very highly significant difference was present between low and high perceived stress group (Table 2). We found that psychosomatic symptoms increased as the self-reported perception of stress increased, irrespective of sex (Fig. 3 and 4). This result is in line with the finding of El Ansari W et al. and Teixeira RJ et al. [28,29]. Our result support the fact that some physical symptoms and diseases are derived from the stresses and strains of everyday living like headache, backpain, high blood pressure [28,8].

There are a number of limitations in our study. The sample size is very small because the response rate of the students was very low. Since the assessment is only based on self-reported questionnaires, recall bias and underreporting or overreporting of the items is also expected. The inclusion of Cardiovascular, Pulmonary parameters and monitoring stress through biomarkers like cortisol could have improved the results. It is also required to investigate the cause of the stress among the students, focusing especially on different psychosocial factors. Also, the correlation between academic performance and stress level needs to be examined.

We recommend that Counselling, social support should be given to the students having difficulty in coping with the academic stresses and the psychosocial environment should be improved in the medical institutions.

We can conclude from our study results that students during their initial period of MBBS curriculum perceive high amount of stress and the stress is associated with psychosomatic symptoms.

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